

On The Symbolic 2-Plithogenic Split-Complex Real Square Matrices and Their Algebraic Properties

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Abstract:

The objective of this paper is to study for the first time the concept of square real matrices with symbolic 2-plithogenic split-complex entries. Many of their algebraic properties will be discussed and handled, where we find the formula of computing inverses, exponents, and powers of these matrices by building a ring isomorphism between the ring of split-complex symbolic 2-plithogenic matrices and the direct product of the symbolic 2-plithogenic matrices with itself. Also, we give the interested reader many related examples to clarify the validity of our work.

Keywords: split-complex number, symbolic 2-plithogenic number, split-complex 2-plithogenic matrix.

Introduction

The concept of symbolic 2-plithogenic rings is considered as a generalization of algebraic rings [1], and these rings were used by many authors to generalize classical algebraic structures such as vector space, modules, and functions into novel symbolic 2-plithogenic and 3-plithogenic versions, see [2-9].

Symbolic 2-plithogenic matrices and other types have been studied in [10], where many results were obtained such as diagonalizations, and eigenvalues.

Symbolic 2-plithogenic split-complex numbers were defined as a combination between split-complex numbers, and symbolic 2-plithogenic numbers, for more details about split-complex structures and their applications, see [11-13]. For similar results about neutrosophic matrices and n-plithogenic matrices check [14-19].

In this paper, we define symbolic 2-plithogenic split-complex matrices, and we present many elementary properties of these matrices, especially those are related to classical matrix theory and applications.

Main Discussion

Definition.

Let $A = (a_{ij})$ be a matrix, it is called symbolic 2-plithogenic split-complex if and only if:

$$a_{ij} = (a_{ij}^{(0)} + a_{ij}^{(1)}P_1 + a_{ij}^{(2)}P_2) + (b_{ij}^{(0)} + b_{ij}^{(1)}P_1 + b_{ij}^{(2)}P_2)J, \quad \text{where} \\ a_{ij}^{(k)}, b_{ij}^{(k)} \in R, J^2 = 1, P_i \times P_j = P_{\max(i,j)}, P_i^2 = P_i.$$

Example.

The matrix $A = \begin{pmatrix} 1 + 2P_1 + P_2 + J(1 - P_2) & (P_1 + P_2)J \\ (2 - P_2) + J(3 + P_1 + P_2) & 5 - (P_1 + 4P_2)J \end{pmatrix}$ is a 2×2 symbolic 2-plithogenic split-complex matrix.

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} 1 + 2P_1 + P_2 & 0 \\ 2 - P_2 & 5 \end{pmatrix} + J \begin{pmatrix} 1 - P_2 & P_1 + P_2 \\ 3 + P_1 + P_2 & -(P_1 + 4P_2) \end{pmatrix}$$

Remark.

Any symbolic 2-plithogenic split-complex matrix can be written as follows $A = T + KJ$; T, K are two symbolic 2-plithogenic real matrices.

Also, it can be written as follows:

$$A = (A_0 + A_1P_1 + A_2P_2) + J(B_0 + B_1P_1 + B_2P_2); A_i, B_i \text{ are classical square real matrices.}$$

The matrix presented in the previous example can be written as:

$$\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 2 & 5 \end{pmatrix} + P_1 \begin{pmatrix} 2 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} + P_2 \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ -1 & 0 \end{pmatrix} + J \left[\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 3 & 0 \end{pmatrix} + P_1 \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 1 & -1 \end{pmatrix} + P_2 \begin{pmatrix} -1 & 1 \\ 1 & -4 \end{pmatrix} \right]$$

Remark.

We denote the ring of all symbolic 2-plithogenic split-complex matrices by $2 - SP_{MS}$.

$(2 - SP_{MS}, +, \cdot)$ is a ring.

Definition.

Let $X = M_0 + N_0J, Y = M_1 + N_1J; M_0, N_0, M_1, N_1 \in 2 - P_M$, then:

$$X + Y = (M_0 + M_1) + (N_0 + N_1)J.$$

$$X.Y = (M_0M_1 + N_0N_1) + (M_0N_1 + N_0M_1)J.$$

Example.

Take:

$$X = \begin{pmatrix} 1 + P_1 & P_2 \\ P_1 & -P_1 + P_2 \end{pmatrix} + J \begin{pmatrix} 2 + P_1 - P_2 & 3P_1 \\ P_1 - P_2 & 2P_2 \end{pmatrix} = M_0 + N_0J$$

$$Y = \begin{pmatrix} 1 + P_1 - P_2 & 2 - P_2 \\ 1 + P_2 & 1 + P_1 \end{pmatrix} + J \begin{pmatrix} 2 - P_2 & P_1 - P_2 \\ 1 + P_1 & P_2 \end{pmatrix} = M_1 + N_1J$$

$$X + Y = \begin{pmatrix} 2 + 2P_1 - P_2 & 2 - P_1 + P_2 \\ 1 + P_1 + P_2 & 1 + P_2 \end{pmatrix} + J \begin{pmatrix} 4 + P_1 - 2P_2 & 4P_1 - P_2 \\ 1 + 2P_1 - P_2 & 3P_2 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$M_0M_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 + P_1 & P_2 \\ P_1 & -P_1 + P_2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 + P_1 - P_2 & 2 - P_2 \\ 1 + P_2 & 1 + P_1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 + 3P_1 & 2 + 2P_2 \\ P_1 & -P_1 + 2P_2 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$N_0N_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 2 + P_1 - P_2 & 3P_1 \\ P_1 - P_2 & 2P_2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 2 - P_2 & P_1 - P_2 \\ 1 + P_1 & P_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 4 + 8P_1 - 4P_2 & 3P_1 \\ 2P_1 + 2P_2 & P_1 + P_2 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$M_0N_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 + P_1 & P_2 \\ P_1 & -P_1 + P_2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 2 - P_2 & P_1 - P_2 \\ 1 + P_1 & P_2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 2 + 2P_1 & 2P_1 - P_2 \\ P_2 & P_1 - P_2 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$N_0M_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 2 + P_1 - P_2 & 3P_1 \\ P_1 - P_2 & 2P_2 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} 1 + P_1 - P_2 & 2 - P_2 \\ 1 + P_2 & 1 + P_1 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 + 7P_1 - P_2 & 4 + 5P_1 - P_2 \\ 2P_1 + 2P_2 & P_1 + 2P_2 \end{pmatrix}$$

So that:

$$X.Y = \begin{pmatrix} 5 + 11P_1 - 4P_2 & 2 + 3P_1 + 2P_2 \\ 3P_1 + 2P_2 & 3P_2 \end{pmatrix} + J \begin{pmatrix} 4 + 9P_1 - P_2 & 2 + 3P_1 + 2P_2 \\ 2P_1 + 3P_2 & 2P_1 + P_2 \end{pmatrix}$$

Theorem.

Let $2 - SP_{MS}$ be the ring of all $n \times n$ symbolic 2-plithogenic split-complex matrices, let $2 - P_M$ be the ring of all $n \times n$ square symbolic 2-plithogenic real matrices, then:

$$f: 2 - SP_{MS} \rightarrow 2 - P_M \times 2 - P_M$$

Such that:

$f(M + NJ) = (M + N, M - N); M, N \in 2 - P_M$ is a ring isomorphism.

Proof.

For $M_0 + N_0J = M_1 + N_1J$, we have:

$$M_0 = M_1, N_0 = N_1, \text{ thus } (M_0 + N_0, M_0 - N_0) = (M_1 + N_1, M_1 - N_1),$$

hence $f(M_0 + N_0J) = f(M_1 + N_1J)$.

For $X = M_0 + N_0J, Y = M_1 + N_1J \in 2 - SP_{MS}$,

we have:

$$f(X + Y) = (M_0 + N_0 + M_1 + N_1, M_0 + M_1 - N_0 - N_1) = f(X) + f(Y).$$

$$f(X.Y) = f[(M_0M_1 + N_0N_1) + (M_0N_1 + N_0M_1)J] = [(M_0 + N_0)(M_1 + N_1), (M_0 - N_0)(M_1 - N_1)] = f(X).f(Y).$$

$$f(X) = 0 \Leftrightarrow \begin{cases} M_0 + N_0 = 0 \\ M_0 - N_0 = 0 \end{cases} \Leftrightarrow M_0 = N_0 = 0$$

Thus, $ker(f) = \{0\}$.

For any arbitrary element $(M, N) \in 2 - P_M \times 2 - P_M$, there exists $X = \frac{1}{2}(M + N) + \frac{1}{2}(M - N)J \in 2 - P_M$, such that $f(X) = (M, N)$, so that f is a ring isomorphism.

Remark.

The inverse isomorphism is:

$$f^{-1}: 2 - P_M \times 2 - P_M \rightarrow 2 - SP_{MS}; f^{-1}(M, N) = \frac{1}{2}(M + N) + \frac{1}{2}(M - N)J.$$

Example.

Consider:

$$X = \begin{pmatrix} 1 + P_1 + P_2 & 3 - P_2 & 1 + P_1 \\ P_1 - P_2 & 5 + P_1 & P_2 \\ P_1 + P_2 & 2P_1 & -P_2 \end{pmatrix} + J \begin{pmatrix} 1 + P_1 - P_2 & 1 & 1 \\ 4 + 2P_1 - P_2 & P_1 & 2P_2 \\ 2P_1 - P_2 & P_1 & 5P_1 \end{pmatrix} = M + NJ,$$

then:

$$f(X) = \left(\begin{pmatrix} 2 + 2P_1 & 4 - P_2 & 1 + P_1 \\ 4 + 3P_1 - 2P_2 & 5 + 2P_1 & 3P_2 \\ 2P_1 & 3P_1 & 5P_1 - P_2 \end{pmatrix}, \begin{pmatrix} 2P_2 & 2 - P_2 & -1 + P_1 \\ -4 - P_1 & 5 & -P_2 \\ -P_1 + 2P_2 & P_1 & -5P_1 - P_2 \end{pmatrix} \right)$$

Results from the isomorphism.

Let $X = M + NJ \in 2 - SP_M; M = M_0 + M_1P_1 + M_2P_2, N = N_0 + N_1P_1 + N_2P_2 \in 2 - P_M$,

then:

1). X is invertible if and only if $M + N, M - N$ are invertible, which is equivalent to:

$$M_0 + N_0, M_0 - N_0, (M_0 + M_1) + (N_0 + N_1), (M_0 + M_1) - (N_0 + N_1), \\ (M_0 + M_1 + M_2) + (N_0 + N_1 + N_2), (M_0 + M_1 + M_2) + (N_0 + N_1 - N_2),$$

Are invertible matrices.

2). If X is invertible, then:

$$X^{-1} = \frac{1}{2}[(M + N)^{-1} + (M - N)^{-1}] + \frac{1}{2}[(M + N)^{-1} - (M - N)^{-1}]J$$

Where:

$$(M + N)^{-1} = (M_0 + N_0)^{-1} + [(M_0 + M_1 + N_0 + N_1)^{-1} - (M_0 + N_0)^{-1}]P_1 \\ + [(M_0 + M_1 + M_2 + N_0 + N_1 + N_2)^{-1} - (M_0 + M_1 + N_0 + N_1)^{-1}]P_2 \\ (M - N)^{-1} = (M_0 - N_0)^{-1} + [(M_0 + M_1 - N_0 - N_1)^{-1} - (M_0 - N_0)^{-1}]P_1 + \\ [(M_0 + M_1 + M_2 - N_0 - N_1 - N_2)^{-1} - (M_0 + M_1 - N_0 - N_1)^{-1}]P_2.$$

$$3). \det X = \frac{1}{2}[\det(M + N) + \det(M - N)] + \frac{1}{2}[\det(M + N) - \det(M - N)]J$$

$$\det(M + N) = \det(M_0 + N_0) + [\det(M_0 + M_1 + N_0 + N_1) - \det(M_0 + N_0)]P_1 + \\ [\det(M_0 + M_1 + M_2 + N_0 + N_1 + N_2) - \det(M_0 + M_1 + N_0 + N_1)]P_2.$$

$$\det(M - N) = \det(M_0 - N_0) + [\det(M_0 + M_1 - N_0 - N_1) - \det(M_0 - N_0)]P_1 + \\ [\det(M_0 + M_1 + M_2 - N_0 - N_1 - N_2) - \det(M_0 + M_1 - N_0 - N_1)]P_2.$$

$$4). X^n = \frac{1}{2}[(M + N)^n + (M - N)^n] + \frac{1}{2}[(M + N)^n - (M - N)^n]J$$

$$(M + N)^n = (M_0 + N_0)^n + [(M_0 + M_1 + N_0 + N_1)^n - (M_0 + N_0)^n]P_1 + [(M_0 + M_1 + \\ M_2 + N_0 + N_1 + N_2)^n - (M_0 + M_1 + N_0 + N_1)^n]P_2.$$

$$(M - N)^n = (M_0 - N_0)^n + [(M_0 + M_1 - N_0 - N_1)^n - (M_0 - N_0)^n]P_1 + [(M_0 + M_1 + \\ M_2 - N_0 - N_1 - N_2)^n - (M_0 + M_1 - N_0 - N_1)^n]P_2.$$

Example.

Consider the following 2×2 symbolic 2-plithogenic split-complex matrix:

$$X = \begin{pmatrix} 2 + \frac{3}{2}P_1 + 4P_2 & \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{3}{2}P_1 & \frac{3}{2} + \frac{1}{2}P_1 + \frac{1}{2}P_2 \end{pmatrix} + J \begin{pmatrix} 1 - \frac{7}{2}P_1 + 2P_2 & \frac{1}{2} - P_1 + P_2 \\ \frac{3}{2}P_1 - 3P_2 & \frac{1}{2} - \frac{3}{2}P_1 - \frac{1}{2}P_2 \end{pmatrix} = M +$$

NJ , where:

$$M = \begin{pmatrix} 2 + \frac{3}{2}P_1 + 4P_2 & \frac{1}{2} \\ \frac{3}{2}P_1 & \frac{3}{2} + \frac{1}{2}P_1 + \frac{1}{2}P_2 \end{pmatrix}, N = \begin{pmatrix} 1 - \frac{7}{2}P_1 + 2P_2 & \frac{1}{2} - P_1 + P_2 \\ \frac{3}{2}P_1 - 3P_2 & \frac{1}{2} - \frac{3}{2}P_1 - \frac{1}{2}P_2 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$M + N = \begin{pmatrix} 3 - P_1 + 6P_2 & 1 - P_1 + P_2 \\ 3P_1 - 3P_2 & 2 - P_1 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$M - N = \begin{pmatrix} 1 + 2P_1 + 2P_2 & P_1 - P_2 \\ 3P_2 & 1 + 2P_1 + P_2 \end{pmatrix}$$

We write:

$M + N = K_0 + K_1P_1 + K_2P_2, M - N = L_0 + L_1P_1 + L_2P_2$, where:

$$K_0 = \begin{pmatrix} 3 & 1 \\ 0 & 2 \end{pmatrix}, K_1 = \begin{pmatrix} -5 & -1 \\ 3 & -1 \end{pmatrix}, K_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 6 & 1 \\ -3 & 0 \end{pmatrix}, K_0 + K_1 = \begin{pmatrix} -2 & 0 \\ 3 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, K_0 + K_1 + K_2 \\ = \begin{pmatrix} 4 & 1 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$L_0 = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, L_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 2 & 1 \\ 0 & 2 \end{pmatrix}, L_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 2 & -1 \\ 3 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, L_0 + L_1 = \begin{pmatrix} 3 & 1 \\ 0 & 3 \end{pmatrix}, L_0 + L_1 + L_2 = \begin{pmatrix} 5 & 0 \\ 3 & 4 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\det(M + N) = \det(K_0) + [\det(K_0 + K_1) - \det(K_0)]P_1 + [\det(K_0 + K_1 + K_2) - \det(K_0 + K_1)]P_2 = 6 + (-2 - 6)P_1 + (4 + 2)P_2 = 6 - 8P_1 + 6P_2.$$

$$\det(M - N) = \det(L_0) + [\det(L_0 + L_1) - \det(L_0)]P_1 + [\det(L_0 + L_1 + L_2) - \det(L_0 + L_1)]P_2 = 1 + (9 - 1)P_1 + (20 - 9)P_2 = 1 + 8P_1 + 11P_2.$$

$$\det X = \frac{1}{2}[\det(M + N) + \det(M - N)] + \frac{1}{2}[\det(M + N) - \det(M - N)] \\ = \frac{1}{2}(7 + 17P_2) + \frac{1}{2}J(5 - 16P_1 - 5P_2) \\ = \left(\frac{7}{2} + \frac{17}{2}P_2\right) + J\left(\frac{5}{2} - 8P_1 - \frac{5}{2}P_2\right)$$

now, let's find the inverse of X :

$$K_0^{-1} = -\frac{1}{6}\begin{pmatrix} 2 & -1 \\ 0 & 3 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{3} & \frac{1}{6} \\ 0 & \frac{1}{2} \end{pmatrix}, (K_0 + K_1)^{-1} = -\frac{1}{2}\begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ -3 & -2 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -\frac{1}{2} & 0 \\ \frac{3}{2} & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$(K_0 + K_1 + K_2)^{-1} = \frac{1}{4}\begin{pmatrix} 1 & -1 \\ 0 & 4 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{4} & -\frac{1}{4} \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$L_0^{-1} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, (L_0 + L_1)^{-1} = \frac{1}{9}\begin{pmatrix} 3 & -1 \\ 0 & 3 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{3} & -\frac{1}{9} \\ 0 & \frac{1}{3} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$(L_0 + L_1 + L_2)^{-1} = \frac{1}{20}\begin{pmatrix} 4 & 0 \\ -3 & 5 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{5} & 0 \\ -\frac{3}{20} & \frac{1}{4} \end{pmatrix}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
(M + N)^{-1} &= (K_0)^{-1} + [(K_0 + K_1)^{-1} - (K_0)^{-1}]P_1 \\
&\quad + [(K_0 + K_1 + K_2)^{-1} - (K_0 + K_1)^{-1}]P_2 \\
&= \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{3} & \frac{1}{6} \\ 0 & \frac{1}{2} \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \frac{-5}{6} & \frac{1}{6} \\ \frac{3}{2} & \frac{1}{2} \end{pmatrix} P_1 + \begin{pmatrix} \frac{3}{4} & \frac{-1}{4} \\ -\frac{3}{2} & 0 \end{pmatrix} P_2 \\
&= \begin{pmatrix} \frac{1}{3} - \frac{5}{6}P_1 + \frac{3}{4}P_2 & \frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{6}P_1 - \frac{1}{4}P_2 \\ \frac{3}{2}P_1 - \frac{3}{2}P_2 & \frac{1}{2} + \frac{1}{2}P_1 \end{pmatrix} \\
(M - N)^{-1} &= (L_0)^{-1} + [(L_0 + L_1)^{-1} - (L_0)^{-1}]P_1 + [(L_0 + L_1 + L_2)^{-1} - (L_0 + L_1)^{-1}]P_2 \\
&= \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix} + \begin{pmatrix} \frac{-2}{3} & \frac{-1}{9} \\ 0 & \frac{-2}{3} \end{pmatrix} P_1 + \begin{pmatrix} \frac{-2}{15} & \frac{1}{9} \\ \frac{-3}{20} & \frac{-1}{12} \end{pmatrix} P_2 \\
&= \begin{pmatrix} 1 - \frac{2}{3}P_1 - \frac{2}{15}P_2 & -\frac{1}{9}P_1 + \frac{1}{9}P_2 \\ -\frac{3}{20}P_2 & 1 - \frac{2}{3}P_1 - \frac{1}{12}P_2 \end{pmatrix}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
X^{-1} &= \frac{1}{2}[(M + N)^{-1} + (M - N)^{-1}] + \frac{1}{2}[(M + N)^{-1} - (M - N)^{-1}]J \\
&= \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} \frac{4}{3} - \frac{3}{2}P_1 + \frac{37}{60}P_2 & -\frac{1}{6} + \frac{1}{18}P_1 - \frac{5}{36}P_2 \\ \frac{3}{2}P_1 - \frac{33}{20}P_2 & \frac{3}{2} - \frac{1}{6}P_1 - \frac{1}{12}P_2 \end{pmatrix} \\
&\quad + \frac{1}{2}J \begin{pmatrix} \frac{-3}{2} - \frac{1}{6}P_1 + \frac{53}{60}P_2 & -\frac{1}{6} + \frac{5}{18}P_1 - \frac{13}{36}P_2 \\ \frac{3}{2}P_1 - \frac{27}{20}P_2 & -\frac{1}{2} + \frac{7}{6}P_1 + \frac{1}{12}P_2 \end{pmatrix} \\
&= \begin{pmatrix} \frac{2}{3} - \frac{3}{4}P_1 + \frac{37}{120}P_2 & -\frac{1}{12} + \frac{1}{36}P_1 - \frac{5}{72}P_2 \\ \frac{3}{4}P_1 - \frac{33}{40}P_2 & \frac{3}{4} - \frac{1}{12}P_1 - \frac{1}{24}P_2 \end{pmatrix} \\
&\quad + J \begin{pmatrix} \frac{-1}{3} - \frac{1}{12}P_1 + \frac{53}{120}P_2 & -\frac{1}{12} + \frac{5}{36}P_1 - \frac{13}{72}P_2 \\ \frac{3}{4}P_1 - \frac{27}{40}P_2 & -\frac{1}{4} + \frac{7}{12}P_1 + \frac{1}{24}P_2 \end{pmatrix}
\end{aligned}$$

As an additional application of the matrix ring isomorphism between $2 - SP_M$ and $2 - P_M \times 2 - P_M$ is to find all possible eigenvalues/vectors for the symbolic 2-plithogenic split-complex matrix.

To find the eigenvalue for a symbolic 2-plithogenic split-complex matrix, we must find all symbolic 2-plithogenic eigen values of $M + N, M - N$.

For the matrix defined in the previous example, we can see:

The eigenvalues of K_0 are $\{3,2\} = Q_0$.

The eigenvalues of $K_0 + K_1$ are $\{-2,1\} = Q_1$.

The eigenvalues of $K_0 + K_1 + K_2$ are $\{4,1\} = Q_2$.

The eigenvalues of $M + N$ are:

$$Q = \{a_0 + (a_1 - a_0)P_1 + (a_2 - a_1)P_2; a_i \in Q_i\} = \{3 - 5P_1 + 6P_2, 3 - 5P_1 + 3P_2, 3 - 2P_1 + 3P_2, 3 - 2P_1, 2 - 4P_1 + 6P_2, 2 - 4P_1 + 3P_2, 2 - P_1 + 3P_2, 2 - P_1\}.$$

The eigenvalue of L_0 is $\{1\} = s_0$.

The eigenvalue of $L_0 + L_1$ is $\{3\} = S_1$.

The eigenvalues of $L_0 + L_1 + L_2$ are $\{5,4\} = S_2$.

The eigenvalues of $M - N$ are:

$$S = \{b_0 + (b_1 - b_0)P_1 + (b_2 - b_1)P_2; b_i \in S_i\} = \{1 + 2P_1 + 2P_2, 1 + 2P_1 + P_2\}$$

The eigen values of the duplet $(M + N, M - N)$ are:

$$\{(3 - 5P_1 + 6P_2, 1 + 2P_1 + 2P_2), (3 - 5P_1 + 6P_2, 1 + 2P_1 + P_2), (3 - 5P_1 + 3P_2, 1 + 2P_1 + P_2), (3 - 5P_1 + 3P_2, 1 + 2P_1 + 2P_2), (3 - 2P_1 + 3P_2, 1 + 2P_1 + 2P_2), (3 - 2P_1 + 3P_2, 1 + 2P_1 + P_2), (2 - P_1, 1 + 2P_1 + 2P_2), (2 - P_1, 1 + 2P_1 + P_2), (2 - 4P_1 + 6P_2, 1 + 2P_1 + 2P_2), (2 - 4P_1 + 6P_2, 1 + 2P_1 + P_2), (2 - 4P_1 + 3P_2, 1 + 2P_1 + 2P_2), (2 - 4P_1 + 3P_2, 1 + 2P_1 + P_2), (2 - P_1 + 3P_2, 1 + 2P_1 + 2P_2), (2 - P_1 + 3P_2, 1 + 2P_1 + P_2), (3 - 2P_1, 1 + 2P_1 + 2P_2), (3 - 2P_1, 1 + 2P_1 + P_2)\}.$$

We put:

$$T_1 = (3 - 5P_1 + 6P_2, 1 + 2P_1 + 2P_2)$$

$$f^{-1}(T_1) = \frac{1}{2}(4 - 3P_1 + 8P_2) + \frac{1}{2}(2 - 7P_1 + 4P_2)J = \left(2 - \frac{3}{2}P_1 + 4P_2\right) + \left(1 - \frac{7}{2}P_1 + 2P_2\right)J.$$

$$T_2 = (3 - 5P_1 + 6P_2, 1 + 2P_1 + P_2)$$

$$f^{-1}(T_2) = \frac{1}{2}(4 - 3P_1 + 7P_2) + \frac{1}{2}(2 - 7P_1 + 5P_2)J = \left(2 - \frac{3}{2}P_1 + \frac{7}{2}P_2\right) + \left(1 - \frac{7}{2}P_1 + \frac{5}{2}P_2\right)J.$$

$$T_3 = (3 - 2P_1 + 3P_2, 1 + 2P_1 + 2P_2)$$

$$f^{-1}(T_3) = \frac{1}{2}(4 + 5P_2) + \frac{1}{2}(2 - 4P_1 + P_2)J = \left(2 + \frac{5}{2}P_2\right) + \left(1 - 2P_1 + \frac{1}{2}P_2\right)J.$$

$$T_4 = (3 - 2P_1 + 3P_2, 1 + 2P_1 + P_2)$$

$$f^{-1}(T_4) = \frac{1}{2}(4 + 4P_2) + \frac{1}{2}(2 - 4P_1 + 2P_2)J = (2 + 2P_2) + (1 - 2P_1 + P_2)J.$$

$$T_5 = (3 - 5P_1 + 3P_2, 1 + 2P_1 + 2P_2)$$

$$f^{-1}(T_5) = \frac{1}{2}(4 - 3P_1 + 5P_2) + \frac{1}{2}(2 - 7P_1 + P_2)J = \left(2 - \frac{3}{2}P_1 + \frac{5}{2}P_2\right) + \left(1 - \frac{7}{2}P_1 + \frac{1}{2}P_2\right)J.$$

$$T_6 = (3 - 5P_1 + 3P_2, 1 + 2P_1 + P_2)$$

$$f^{-1}(T_6) = \frac{1}{2}(4 - 3P_1 + 4P_2) + \frac{1}{2}(2 - 7P_1 + 2P_2)J = \left(2 - \frac{3}{2}P_1 + 2P_2\right) + \left(1 - \frac{7}{2}P_1 + P_2\right)J.$$

$$T_7 = (2 - P_1, 1 + 2P_1 + 2P_2)$$

$$f^{-1}(T_7) = \frac{1}{2}(3 + P_1 + 2P_2) + \frac{1}{2}(1 - 3P_1 - 2P_2)J = \left(\frac{3}{2} + \frac{1}{2}P_1 + P_2\right) + \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{3}{2}P_1 - P_2\right)J.$$

$$T_8 = (2 - P_1, 1 + 2P_1 + P_2)$$

$$f^{-1}(T_8) = \frac{1}{2}(3 + P_1 + P_2) + \frac{1}{2}(1 - 3P_1 - P_2)J = \left(\frac{3}{2} + \frac{1}{2}P_1 + \frac{1}{2}P_2\right) + \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{3}{2}P_1 - \frac{1}{2}P_2\right)J.$$

$$T_9 = (2 - 4P_1 + 6P_2, 1 + 2P_1 + 2P_2)$$

$$f^{-1}(T_9) = \frac{1}{2}(3 - 2P_1 + 8P_2) + \frac{1}{2}(1 - 6P_1 + 4P_2)J = \left(\frac{3}{2} - P_1 + 4P_2\right) + \left(\frac{1}{2} - 3P_1 + 2P_2\right)J.$$

$$T_{10} = (2 - 4P_1 + 6P_2, 1 + 2P_1 + P_2)$$

$$f^{-1}(T_{10}) = \frac{1}{2}(3 - 2P_1 + 7P_2) + \frac{1}{2}(1 - 6P_1 + 5P_2)J = \left(\frac{3}{2} - P_1 + \frac{7}{2}P_2\right) + \left(\frac{1}{2} - 3P_1 + \frac{5}{2}P_2\right)J.$$

$$T_{11} = (2 - 4P_1 + 6P_2, 1 + 2P_1 + 2P_2)$$

$$f^{-1}(T_{11}) = \frac{1}{2}(3 - 2P_1 + 5P_2) + \frac{1}{2}(1 - 6P_1 + P_2)J = \left(\frac{3}{2} - P_1 + \frac{5}{2}P_2\right) + \left(\frac{1}{2} - 3P_1 + \frac{1}{2}P_2\right)J.$$

$$T_{12} = (2 - 4P_1 + 3P_2, 1 + 2P_1 + P_2)$$

$$f^{-1}(T_{12}) = \frac{1}{2}(3 - 2P_1 + 4P_2) + \frac{1}{2}(1 - 6P_1 + 2P_2)J = \left(\frac{3}{2} - P_1 + 2P_2\right) + \left(\frac{1}{2} - 3P_1 + P_2\right)J.$$

$$T_{13} = (2 - P_1 + 3P_2, 1 + 2P_1 + 2P_2)$$

$$f^{-1}(T_{13}) = \frac{1}{2}(3 + P_1 + 5P_2) + \frac{1}{2}(1 - 3P_1 + P_2)J = \left(\frac{3}{2} + \frac{1}{2}P_1 + \frac{5}{2}P_2\right) + \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{3}{2}P_1 + \frac{1}{2}P_2\right)J.$$

$$T_{14} = (2 - P_1 + 3P_2, 1 + 2P_1 + P_2)$$

$$f^{-1}(T_{14}) = \frac{1}{2}(3 + P_1 + 4P_2) + \frac{1}{2}(1 - 3P_1 + 2P_2)J = \left(\frac{3}{2} + \frac{1}{2}P_1 + 2P_2\right) + \left(\frac{1}{2} - \frac{3}{2}P_1 + P_2\right)J.$$

$$T_{15} = (3 - 2P_1, 1 + 2P_1 + 2P_2)$$

$$f^{-1}(T_{15}) = \frac{1}{2}(4 + 2P_2) + \frac{1}{2}(2 - 4P_1 - 2P_2)J = (2 + P_2) + (1 - 2P_1 - P_2)J.$$

$$T_{16} = (3 - 2P_1, 1 + 2P_1 + P_2)$$

$$f^{-1}(T_{16}) = \frac{1}{2}(4 + P_2) + \frac{1}{2}(2 - 4P_1 - P_2)J = \left(2 + \frac{1}{2}P_2\right) + \left(1 - 2P_1 - \frac{1}{2}P_2\right)J.$$

Conclusion

In this paper, we studied for the first time the concept of square real matrices with symbolic 2-plithogenic split-complex entries, where we find the formula of computing inverses, exponents, and powers of these matrices by building a ring isomorphism between the ring of split-complex symbolic 2-plithogenic matrices and the direct product of the symbolic 2-plithogenic matrices with itself. Also, we give the interested reader many related examples to clarify the validity of our work.

References

1. Merkepçi, H., and Abobala, M., " On The Symbolic 2-Plithogenic Rings", International Journal of Neutrosophic Science, 2023.
2. M. B. Zeina, N. Altounji, M. Abobala, and Y. Karmouta, "Introduction to Symbolic 2-Plithogenic Probability Theory," *Galoitica: Journal of Mathematical Structures and Applications*, vol. 7, no. 1, 2023.
3. Ben Othman, K., Von Shtawzen, O., Khaldi, A., and Ali, R., "On The Concept Of Symbolic 7-Plithogenic Real Matrices", *Pure Mathematics For Theoretical Computer Science*, Vol.1, 2023.

4. Ben Othman, K., Von Shtawzen, O., Khaldi, A., and Ali, R., "On The Symbolic 8-Plithogenic Matrices", Pure Mathematics For Theoretical Computer Science, Vol.1, 2023.
5. Nader Mahmoud Taffach , Ahmed Hatip., "A Review on Symbolic 2-Plithogenic Algebraic Structures " Galoitica Journal Of Mathematical Structures and Applications, Vol.5, 2023.
6. Nader Mahmoud Taffach , Ahmed Hatip.," A Brief Review on The Symbolic 2-Plithogenic Number Theory and Algebraic Equations " , Galoitica Journal Of Mathematical Structures and Applications, Vol.5, 2023.
7. Ali, R., and Hasan, Z., "An Introduction To The Symbolic 3-Plithogenic Vector Spaces", Galoitica Journal Of Mathematical Structures and Applications, vol. 6, 2023.
8. Rawashdeh, A., "An Introduction To The Symbolic 3-plithogenic Number Theory", Neoma Journal Of Mathematics and Computer Science, 2023.
9. Ben Othman, K., "On Some Algorithms For Solving Symbolic 3-Plithogenic Equations", Neoma Journal Of Mathematics and Computer Science, 2023.
10. Alfahal, A.; Alhasan, Y.; Abdulfatah, R.; Mehmood, A.; Kadhim, M. On Symbolic 2-Plithogenic Real Matrices and Their Algebraic Properties. *Int. J. Neutrosophic Sci.* **2023**, *21*.
11. Khaldi, A., " A Study On Split-Complex Vector Spaces", Neoma Journal Of Mathematics and Computer Science, 2023.
12. Ahmad, K., " On Some Split-Complex Diophantine Equations", Neoma Journal Of Mathematics and Computer Science, 2023.
13. Merkepçi, M., and Abobala, M., " On Some Novel Results About Split-Complex Numbers, The Diagonalization Problem And Applications To

- Public Key Asymmetric Cryptography", Journal of Mathematics, Hindawi, 2023.
14. Abobala, M., Hatip, A., and Bal, M., " A Review On Recent Advantages In Algebraic Theory Of Neutrosophic Matrices", International Journal of Neutrosophic Science, Vol.17, 2021.
 15. Abobala, M. On Refined Neutrosophic Matrices and Their Applications in Refined Neutrosophic Algebraic Equations. *J. Math.* **2021**, 2021, 5531093.
 16. Abobala, M., On Refined Neutrosophic Matrices and Their Applications In Refined Neutrosophic Algebraic Equations, Journal Of Mathematics, Hindawi, 2021
 17. Olgun, N., Hatip, A., Bal, M., and Abobala, M., " A Novel Approach To Necessary and Sufficient Conditions For The Diagonalization of Refined Neutrosophic Matrices", International Journal of neutrosophic Science, Vol. 16, pp. 72-79, 2021.
 18. Hatip, A., " On The Algebraic Properties of Symbolic n-Plithogenic Matrices For n=5, n=6", Galoitica Journal of Mathematical Structures and Applications, 2023.
 19. Merkepçi, H., "On Novel Results about the Algebraic Properties of Symbolic 3-Plithogenic and 4-Plithogenic Real Square Matrices", Symmetry, MDPI, 2023.

Received 29/5/2023, Accepted 22/9/2023